

2.0 To Study the Mental Health and its Relationship with Spiritual Intelligence of Undergraduate Students

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Abstract

The current investigation was conducted with the purpose of analysing the relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students. The research was conducted over 350 undergraduate students enrolled in different government university in Lucknow district. Among the aforementioned sample, the male gender was represented by a total of 110 individuals, while the female gender was represented by a count of 240 individuals. Mental Health Battery by A. K. Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta and Spiritual Intelligence Scale by K. S. Misrawere used to obtain data from sample. The study revealed a positive and significant relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students.

Keywords: Mental Health, Spiritual Intelligence

Introduction

Mental health has emerged as one of the most pressing issues facing the modern society. Maintaining a healthy mental state is one of the prerequisites for an individual's overall growth and development. However, due to the increased industrialization and complexity of the modern social system, it has become difficult for an individual to strike a healthy balance between himself and his social surroundings. Young individuals worldwide experience distress due to inadequate mental health. According to UNICEF (n.d.), it is a leading contributor to mortality, morbidity, and dysfunction, particularly among the elderly adolescent population. In the last few years, the media have reported an alarming rise in the number of instances of suicide and killing that mostly evade the educational system. This is especially true for adolescents attending university, as they are most likely to experience frustration due to the pressure exerted on them by their professors, parents and society, in addition to other factors such as competition and high aspirations. The mental problems commonly begin in childhood and adolescence but are not treated until years later (Kessler et al., 2007; & Patel et al., 2007). In numerous studies, it has been observed that approximately 50% of mental disorders that persist throughout an individual's lifetime originate during adolescence, while 75% of such conditions emerge by the age of 25. Even though interventions for early-stage disorders might help reduce the severity and length of primary disorders and stop secondary disorders from happening, more study is needed immediately to improve affordable and doable interventions. According to a survey report by Worsley and Williams (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has the potential to significantly impact nationwide mental health both presently and in the long term. The report emphasizes the need for prioritizing mental health research as a crucial component of the global effort to respond to the epidemic. As a result, the importance of mental health has become more widely recognised in all facets of society, which is particularly relevant in education.

Mental Health

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines mental health as "a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her abilities, can deal with the typical tribulations of life, can work productively, and can make a positive contribution to his or her community." The contemporary widely-accepted interpretation of health is expressed in Sushruta Samhita-

“Samadosha, Samagnischa, Samadhatumalkriyah!

Prasannatmendriyamanah, Swasthaitiabhidhiyate”!! (Su.Su. 15/10)

This phrase is commonly used in traditional Indian medicine to describe a state of optimal health and well-being. This phrase conveys the state of equilibrium in tridosha, the thirteen agni or metabolic fires, the seven dhatu or tissues, and the filtering procedures of contaminants. This definition encompasses both the aspects of physical and mental health. The definition's verse "PrasannatmendriyaManah" is considered fundamental to achieving mental well-being (ManasSwastha). The above definition of health is quite similar to the one provided by the World Health Organization (WHO). It is noteworthy that Ayurveda has espoused the same principles that the World Health Organization currently acknowledges.

Mental health is not just the lack of mental illness; it is more about the daily things we do to keep our minds strong. Optimal psychological well-being is characterized by the absence of mental illness or disorders and the presence of positive qualities such as resilience, emotional regulation, and a sense of purpose (Singh, 2004). Mental health refers to an individual's capacity to adapt effectively to the diverse stressors encountered in their environment throughout their lifespan. Mental health is a state of well-being, drive for life, and a sense that the individual is utilizing his abilities and expertise (Anderson, 1998). Good mental health significantly enhances the holistic health and wellness of individuals and their communities. The benefits of maintaining good mental health throughout all stages of life cannot be overstated, as it has the potential to impact one's physical well-being. From a social perspective, mental health is widely regarded as a valuable resource that contributes positively to individual, social, and economic asset development (Dwivedi & Harper, 2004).

Concerns about one's mental health are linked to the development of a 'holistic' integrated personality, which is differentiated by the integrity of the different aspects of one's self rather than the categorisation of those components. Therefore, a well-balanced mind yields a well-rounded personality. India has a rich cultural heritage, and over the centuries, its people have developed various strategies to deal with different problems.

Spiritual Intelligence

Intelligence can be defined as the cognitive capacity that enables an individual to make decisions and carry out tasks. The conventional notion of intelligence, commonly called the intelligence quotient, has been a fundamental concept in global discourse.

correlational analysis to determine the relationships between the defined variables, including mental health and spiritual Intelligence.

Population of the study

The study population consisted of all undergraduates who were in their second year of study and enrolled in government universities in Lucknow city. The University of Lucknow and the KMC Language University, Lucknow, were selected using a convenience sampling strategy for the study.

Sampling method and sample of the study

The present research study was conducted on a randomly selected sample of 350 undergraduate second-year students. Out of these 350 students, 240 belonged to the University of Lucknow, Lucknow, while the remaining 110 studied at KMC Language University. The total number of male students enrolled in the BA second year is 110, and the total number of female students is estimated at 240.

Tools of study

Mental Health Battery by A. K. Singh and Alpana Sen Gupta (2019)

Spiritual Intelligence Scale by K. S. Misra (2014)

Results

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students.

Table 1: The correlation coefficients between mental health and spiritual intelligence among undergraduate students (Total score).

Variables	N	Correlation 'r'	Sig. (2-tailed)
Mental Health	350	.330**	.000
Spiritual Intelligence	350		

** Significant at 0.05 level, df= 348

The correlation between the students' overall mental health and spiritual intelligence is presented in Table-1. The table displays the data in terms of the student's total scores. The value of the Pearson correlation coefficient, denoted by 'r', is determined to be 0.330 (df=348), and the value of 'p' for this correlation is 0.000, indicating that it is significant and positive. Therefore, under these conditions, the null hypothesis is rejected, which states that there is no significant relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students, and the research hypothesis is accepted.

H₀1 (a): There is no significant relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students in relation to gender.

is accepted, which states that there is no significant relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of rural students, and the research hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion on the Findings

The first major objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students. The findings from Table 1 indicate a statistically significant and positive correlation between mental health and spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students. Furthermore, the tabulated results are consistent with the outcomes documented by Arubuola (2023); Patel and Veidlinger (2023) and Bös et al. (2023).

Thakur (2016) and Kaur (2017) have demonstrated a noteworthy correlation between mental health and spiritual intelligence, taking into account gender and location. Based on the student's educational backgrounds, Pant and Srivastava (2019); and Mohammadyari (2012) also made reference to such a relationship. However, the research indicates a negative and insignificant relationship between the mental well-being of rural students and their level of spiritual intelligence. The results align with the research conducted by Nath and Saikia (2020); and Kaplin et al. (2017) on the correlation between spiritual intelligence and mental health indicators. People who are in a state of good mental health feel sad, ill, furious, or unhappy, and this is a natural aspect of a life that has been completely experienced by a human being (Waterman, 1993; Lamers et al., 2011). It is essential to keep in mind that both spiritual intelligence and mental health are multidimensional and intricate concepts and that the relationship between the two can change depending on the person and their surroundings. While some people may find peace and encouragement in their relationship with spirituality, others may not identify with the practices or beliefs associated with spirituality. When it comes to issues pertaining to one's mental and spiritual health, it is absolutely necessary to recognize and honor the distinct viewpoints and experiences of each individual.

Conclusion

The research presents comprehensive findings pertaining to the mental health of spiritual intelligence of undergraduate students. The study examined the variables within an academic context, utilizing a sample population consisting solely of undergraduate students from the Lucknow district, Uttar Pradesh, India. The investigation unveiled that mental health and spiritual intelligence was noteworthy. There exists a positive correlation between spiritual intelligence and mental health of undergraduate students.

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